

Different ways of calculating ideal speed of sound and internal pressure, and their excess counterparts^ψ

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A number of approximations have been proposed to obtain the ideal contribution to excess speeds of sound and internal pressures.

In recent years there has been considerable attention given on the interpretation of the experimental speeds of sound or internal pressures of liquid mixtures, in terms of departures from their ideal values. A survey of the literature shows that the speed of sound or internal pressure properties of ideal liquid mixtures is wrongly defined and calculated. Although it is by no means straight forward. As a result different values of excess quantities are obtained.

Consequently, it is helpful to understand the various approaches that have been used to obtain the ideal contribution to excess speeds of sound and internal pressures. Identification of subtle errors that are associated with these approaches have been illustrated for binary liquid mixtures of 2-propanol + octane and 2-methoxyethanol + water mixtures at 298.15 K.

Theory :

The excess quantity Z^E , by definition, represents the excess of the given property Z of a real mixture over Z^{id} , the value for an ideal mixture at the same temperature, pressure, and composition :

$$Z^E = Z - Z^{id} \quad (1)$$

The accuracy of values of Z^E depends not only on the accuracy of the experimental quantity Z but also on the accuracy of any approximation adopted in evaluating Z^{id} . A literature¹⁻³ search has clearly revealed some misconceptions about the calculations of Z^{id} . These errors are generally due to incorrect formulation of the ideal mixing law. The subject has been thoroughly reviewed by the Douheret *et al.*⁴

In the present paper the influence of different approximations made by various authors in evaluating the ideal contribution to excess speeds of sound and internal pressures have been examined. For this purpose, the results for binary mixtures recently studied either in our laboratory or others have been utilized.

Working equations :

Approximate approaches to the ideal speed of sound :

Numerous approximate ideal mixing rules have been proposed to estimate ideal speed of sound u^{id} . The methods differ and they are all approximate. For example, the ultrasonic speed in ideal liquid mixtures of organic compounds was considered to be the mass fraction w_i weighted average of those of the speeds in the pure components u_i^+ , and calculated from eq. (2)⁵ :

$$u^{id} = \sum_i w_i u_i^+ \quad (2)$$

The most frequently encountered error has been the assumption that u^{id} is the mole fraction x_i weighted average of the values of its pure components u_i^+ with the following expression^{2,6-8} (approximation I) :

$$u^{id} = \sum_i x_i u_i^+ \quad (3)$$

Use of eq. (3), the quantity calculated from eq. (1) is sometimes erroneously identified as an excess ultrasonic speed or 'apparent excess speed of sound', Δu . The 'excess' means that, for a binary liquid mixtures having ideal thermodynamic properties, thermodynamic does not require the ul-

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trasonic speed to be a linear function of the mole fraction composition. These terms should be avoided in the discussion of Δu . The variations of the values of u^E for 2-propanol-octane mixtures is shown in Fig. 1 as a function of 2-propanol (x), calculated from the data given by Tojo *et al.*⁹.

However, the u^{id} has sometimes been approximated by the volume fraction average¹⁰ (approximation II) :

$$u^{id} = \sum_i \phi_i u_i^+ \quad (4)$$

The calculated values of u^E obtained from eqs. (1) and (4) for the same 2-propanol-octane system differ from those of u^E (approximation I) and are given as a function of x in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Excess speed of sound u^E for mixtures of 2-propanol and octane at 298.15 K, as a function of the concentration of 2-propanol : (1) $u^{E(x)}$ (approximation I); (2) $u^{E(\phi)}$ (approximation II); (3) u^E (approximation III); (4) u^E (approximation IV); (5) u^E (approximation V).

Another approach was used to calculate the ultrasonic ideal behavior in 2-(2-alkoxyethoxy)ethanol-water mixtures¹¹ (approximation III) :

$$u^{id} = [(\sum x_i \rho_i^+) \kappa_s^{id}]^{-1/2} \quad (5)$$

Calculation of density in ideal mixtures has sometimes been equated¹² by a volume-fraction averaging instead of mole fraction averaging. So, it appears that the approach based on eq. (5) is doubtful for defining an ideal thermodynamic value for the speed of sound in a mixture. The calculated values of u^E obtained from eqs. (1) and (5) for the same binary mixtures are shown in Fig. 1. The curve is in fact quite different from those of the approaches described here.

The formulation of u^{id} is more complex; a thermodynamically sound eq. (6) was proposed¹² (approximation IV) :

$$u^{id} = [\sum \phi_i^2 (C_{p,i}^+ / C_{v,i}^+) (C_{v,m}^{id} / C_{p,m}^{id}) (1/w_i (u_i^+)^2)]^{-1/2} \quad (6)$$

This equation is a slightly simplified form of equation given by Van Dael and Vangeel¹³.

In so far as the Newton-Laplace equation is valid, the ideal ultrasonic speed u^{id} may be expressed correctly in terms of thermodynamic quantities of an ideal mixture (approximation V)¹⁴ :

$$u^{id} = V_m^{id} [M_m K_{s,m}^{id}]^{-1/2} \quad (7)$$

This approach is the same as those used to determine the ideal isentropic compressibility. Using eq. (7), the quantity calculated from eq. (1) is sometimes called the deviation of ultrasonic speed u^D ¹⁵, which seems to be more correct. In literatures, this quantity was referred to as an 'excess' ultrasonic speed. It is not appropriate to speak of an excess intensive property^{16,17}. Excess quantities u^E based on approximation V were calculated for the same binary mixtures and are plotted in Fig. 1 as a function of x . The u^E values lie in between the values of u^E (approximation I and V).

Curves for u^E based on approximation IV were calculated for the same binary systems and are induced in Fig. 1 as a function of x for comparison. The values obtained from IV are quite close to the values obtained from I. The values obtained from II (in comparison to the approximation III) are highly negative whereas the values obtained from IV (in comparison to the approximation V) are less negative. The u^E values calculated on the basis of approximation IV show smallest discrepancy corresponding to the values from I and V. True thermodynamic excess speeds (approximation V) appear to be much larger than the values calculated on the basis of approximation IV.

Approximate approaches to the ideal mixing rules for the internal pressure :

For intensive properties like internal pressure, the departures (or deviations) from ideality should be referred to as such rather than an excess internal pressure. Although the term excess internal pressure has been used in the literature¹⁸⁻²⁰, its use is not acceptable. Now, inspection of the literature reveals that for internal pressure properties, the ideal mixing law has been chosen erroneously but not defined clearly. The different expressions on ideal mixing law allow to calculate the deviations in the internal pressure, giving rise to different values and the interpretations were made accordingly. The present paper examines the influence of two different approximations commonly used in evaluating the deviations in internal pressure.

In the estimation of ideal internal pressure P_{int}^{pid} for mixtures, various authors have assumed^{3,20-22} that P_{int}^{id} is the

additivity of internal pressures of pure substances $P_{int,i}^+$ in the mole fraction x_i scale average (approximation I) :

$$P_{int}^{id} = \sum x_i P_{int,i}^+ \quad (8)$$

This is not the correct thermodynamic method for obtaining P_{int}^{id} . However, the quantity calculated from eqs. (1) and (8), is sometimes called the deviation of internal pressure¹. The term deviation is preferable because the internal pressure is an intensive property.

Thermodynamically, the isothermal internal energy divided by the molar volume coefficients of liquids measure the internal pressure :

$$P_{int} = (\partial U / \partial V)_T \quad (9)$$

where U is the internal energy, V is the volume and T the temperature.

Making use of coefficients of thermal expansion α and isothermal compressibility, κ_T , internal pressure can be expressed as²³ :

$$P_{int} = (\partial U / \partial V)_T = (\alpha T / \kappa_T) - P \quad (10)$$

At zero pressure,

$$P_{int} = (\alpha_p T / \kappa_T) \quad (11)$$

To obtain a correct formula for the internal pressure of a thermodynamically ideal mixture, eq. (9) should be transformed to the molar properties $K_{T,m}$ and $A_{P,m}$ from the corresponding properties of κ_T and α_p . Eq. (10) should be written as :

$$P_{int} = T A_{P,m} / K_{T,m} - P \quad (12)$$

Indeed, κ_T and α_p can be defined by eqs. (13) and (14) :

$$\kappa_T = -1/V_m (\partial V_m / \partial P)_T \quad (13)$$

$$\alpha_p = 1/V_m (\partial V_m / \partial T)_p \quad (14)$$

Although the internal pressure is a non-Gibbsian property²⁴, whereas $K_{T,m}^{id}$ and $A_{P,m}^{id}$ are Gibbsian quantities. Both $K_{T,m}$ and $A_{P,m}$ for a thermodynamically ideal mixture are the mole-fraction weighted average of the pure component properties :

$$K_{T,m}^{id} = \sum x_i K_{T,i}^+ \quad (15)$$

$$A_{P,m}^{id} = \sum x_i A_{P,i}^+ \quad (16)$$

From eqs. (15) and (16), we may write eq. (10) :

$$P_{int}^{id} = T A_{P,m}^{id} / K_{T,m}^{id} - P = \frac{\sum x_i T A_{P,i}^+ K_{T,i}^+ / K_{T,i}^+}{\sum x_i K_{T,i}^+} - P$$

$$= \frac{\sum x_i K_{T,i}^+ (P_{int,i}^+ + P)}{\sum x_i K_{T,i}^+} - P \quad (17)$$

After a simple transformation, we finally obtain the correct formula for the internal pressure in the thermodynamically ideal mixtures²⁵ (approximation II) :

$$P_{int}^{id} = \sum \varphi_i P_{int,i}^+ \quad (18)$$

where

$$\varphi_K = x_K K_{T,K}^+ / \sum x_i K_{T,i}^+ \quad (19)$$

In order to illustrate the difference between the excess internal pressure (eqs. (1) and (18)) and the quasi-excess us-

Fig. 2. Deviations of the internal pressure for mixtures of (a) 2-methoxyethanol-water; (b) 2-propanol-octane at 298.15 K, as a function of concentration of 2-methoxyethanol or 2-propanol : (—) deviations from additivity given by eq. (8) and (---) the thermodynamic excess calculated from eq. (18).

ing eqs. (1) and (8), we used the data obtained by our laboratory for 2-methoxyethanol + water and by Tojo *et al.*⁹ for 2-propanol + octane systems (Fig. 2). The evidence provided by Fig. 2 for the 2-methoxyethanol + water system is striking. True thermodynamic excess internal pressures (approximation II) appear to be lower than the values calculated on the basis of approximate model I for the ideal internal pressure. Thus, it is evident that the deviation calculated by eqs. (1) and (8), is not a correct approximation of the excess internal pressure. Furthermore, deviation cannot

be explained in terms of molecular interactions in such a straightforward way as suggested sometimes in literature. However, if the mixture components (2-propanol and water) have similar compression⁹ and the excess internal pressure is small, the difference between the excess (eqs. (1) and (8)) and the deviation (eqs. (1) and (18)) is also small as in Fig. 2.

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